

A Multimodal Biometric Authentication System for People Identification Using Custom Score Fusion Algorithm

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Abstract

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Recent findings suggest that biometric authentication has a lot to do with cybersecurity processes, which verifies user's identity by using their unique biological traits that include fingerprints, facial features, voices and retinas but its drawback also involves identity theft and person mismatch. The Biometric authentication systems mainly store the information they obtain in order to verify a user's identity when a person accesses his or her account. There are a lot of defects in this type of authentication which is sometimes insecure than traditional forms of multi-factor authentication. This paper provides an inept means of design by automating the biometric mode as a form of multimodal authentication to counteract identity theft using a custom score fusion algorithm. It considers the facial features with the eye retina and fingerprint to accurately identify a person in multi-neutral settings involving a database of collected images. The future perspective is to demonstrate this in real-time and embed virtual image processing for online facial image recognition.

Keywords: Multimodal biometric identification, Image processes, fingerprint authentication, Traditional multi-factor authentication, Eye retina, Image recognition.

1 Introduction

In modern-day technology, biometric authentication and its uses have a number of advantages with digital applications. It provides answers to a lot of things a person has and helps verify identity. It also provides access to user experience with high convenience and rapid authentication, it could also be non-transferable such that everyone has access to a unique set of biometrics with a spoof-proof authentication thereby hard to fake or steal.

Its access provides increased levels of assurance to providers to authenticate a person's identity as tangible in a real-world scenario. On the other hand, multimodal deep learning in the context of biometrics often encounters significant challenges due to the dependence on utterances of long speech and images, which are sometimes impractical in most situations. [1] in their paper presents a novel solution addressing some of these issues by leveraging ultrashort

voice utterances and depth video of the mouth section for person identification. They proposed a method that utilizes an amalgamation of residual neural networks to encode depth videos and a novel delay neural network architecture that encodes voice signals. This is in an effort to fuse information from these different modalities, they integrated self-attention and engineered a noise-resistance model that effectively manages diverse types of noise, their approach exhibits superior performance over the existing methods through rigorous testing on a benchmark dataset and this resulted in an average improvement of 10%. The method is seen to be efficient for scenarios where there are extended utterances and RGB images are impractical or impossible. It was noted that its potential extends to different multimodal applications that are beyond just person identification. This paper focuses on a novel algorithm that uses a custom score fusion rule from a database of images and fingerprints to identify the person being searched for (Figure 3) where the end product is to identify whether the person is genuine or an imposter. The search pattern is mostly located in the region of the nose and mouth section with a cascaded pattern search. The user experience is first investigated in this section because this serves as one of the main factors for a multimodal biometric system.

The user experience is very expedient and fast while the initial process for biometric authentication is technical from the user's point of view is unbelievably informal and swift. Sometimes placing a finger on a scanner and unlocking an account within seconds is incredibly faster than simply typing out a long password that consists of a manifold of distinct characters. Also, loss of memory with a password is a common mistake of most users the chances of forgetting one's own biometric are known to be unusual because there are no such cases. Biometric authentication is non-transferable because its input is present upon authorization. The only means to use most biometric authentication is with a physical application since one can't transfer or share a physical biometric in digital form. Most biometrics is spoof-proof, e.g. face patterns, iris scanning and fingerprints, while others are near impossible to replicate with current technology. There are over sixty-four billion changes that a person's fingerprint with match up exactly with another person's own or someone else's [10, 8, 16, 3]. According to [11, 17, 12], in a different way, one has a chance of winning the lottery than having a similar fingerprint as a hacker who is trying to get one's account information that is secured by biometrics (Figure 2).

2 Literature Review

Given its advantages, like increased security, convenience and efficiency, there are also some drawbacks, like significant investment in cost needed in biometrics for security, data breaches for biometric databases being liable

to hacking, tracking and data on biometrics devices like facial recognition systems that have limited privacy for the users [13, 19, 22, 5]. Bia is one of its drawbacks in machine learning algorithms which has to be very advanced to minimize false positive cases in biometric demographic bias and also inaccuracy by falsely rejecting and accepting person identities which can occur and prevent selection of users from accessing the systems. It is not a new thing that a more advanced security system would need important investments and costs to implement secure biometric authentication. According to [4, 14, 9, 7, 20], in a survey conducted in 2018 by Spiceworks, 67% of IT professionals cite that cost is the biggest reason for not adopting biometric authentication. The company would have to pay for transitioning to a biometric authentication which is not the only thing they would pay for, with 47% of the surveyed addressing the need to upgrade the current systems in the process to support the shift to biometric authentication on the devices they use.

Users' personal data collected by governments and businesses are under constant attacks and threats from hackers. This is because data is irreplaceable and organizations require that sensitive biometric data be treated with increased security and caution. This is a most expensive prospect and technically it is difficult to stay ahead of fraud advancements. There is always the possibility of changing a password or pin if it is compromised, but such can't be said for a person's behavioural and physiological biometrics. In systems like other biometric security and facial recognition technology, the privacy of users requires to be taken into consideration as the world increases its use of biometric authentication systems. A user runs the risk of leaving a permanent digital record that can be potentially tracked by nefarious actors when biometrics are converted into data and stored especially in places and countries that have huge amounts of surveillance measures. Most governments and organisations in many instances have used facial recognition software to track and identify most people with scary accuracy that most knowingly hinders privacy [2, 15, 18, 23]. With or without a person's knowledge, biometric data can become a permanent digital tag that can be used to track the person's surveillance with the increase of biometric data.

Minimising demographic bias in biometrics is one of the drawbacks of verifying applicant's identities during digital onboarding and this is a challenge for providers. Deliberate misuse can result in discrimination and exclusion, particularly with poor implementation of technology. Without a proven, cross-demographic performance, document-centric identity-proofing solutions can be unreliable and limit customer access to essentials like expanding the range of digital services and credit.

A research team [24, 21, 6] from New York University created an Artificial intelligence (AI) platform which was

Figure 1: A multimodal biometric system made up of a fingerprint and a face sensor, whose match scores are combined through a fusion rule.

Figure 2: Hacker who is trying to get one's account information that is secured by biometrics.

able to falsely crack fingerprint authentication at a high success rate of 20% by identical comparison of partial prints to full biometric data. The most common biometric authentication process depends on partial information to verify a person's identity. A mobile biometric device can scan an entire fingerprint to facial images during the enrollment phase which is converted into data. The future biometric authentication of facial and fingerprint will only use parts of the prints and facial images to verify and identify a person and this is faster and quicker. A combination of physical and behavioural authentication enhances the security posture from a malicious actor

who tries to spoof fingerprints and can detect change in behaviour and deny entry. This paper demonstrates the use of multimodal biometric authentication with a custom score fusion algorithm that can rapidly identify a person's information with the scheme of cost or bias features i.e., it is aimed at reducing the disadvantages mentioned above and focus mostly on reducing false positive and mismatches in person identification. The method adopted is discussed in the proceeding section.

3 Method

In the operational stage, the detected facial image is projected onto the same eigenspace, and the similarity between the input facial image and fingerprint and the template is computed into the eigenspace.

$$F_2 (\delta_2^0, \delta_2^1) = -\|\delta_2^1 - \delta_2^0\| \quad (1)$$

The multimodal biometric used here is the combination of multiple biometric recognition sources that provide a more reliable verification and identification decision fusion making. The fusion of multi-biometric sources is performed on a different level that includes score level, features and data. The method presents a comprehensive view of the multi-modal score level fusion decision problem together with the proposed and future solution which has already been presented in the literature. The discussion of the result is made to give a view on the comparative result between multi-biometric fusion in all the scenarios. The present window form of the results

Figure 3: Authentication with a custom score fusion algorithm that can rapidly identify a person's information.

is aimed at providing a clearer view of the future perspective especially under the identify score and person demography where there are a lot of related applications which are rapidly growing in areas like pervasive surveillance and forensics.

3.1 Databases

To build and evaluate an optimized multimodal biometry fusion system, a large and diverse informative dataset of images and fingerprints is collected. For this case, the database contains matching scores from multimodal resources for both importers and genuine matches as also collected which are required. There are four publicly available databases that we considered. The Google images, XM2VTS Score-level Fusion Benchmark Dataset (Poh and Bengio, 2006), which contains a database of scores taken from experiments carried out on the XM2VTS, images from the NASARAWA state university (NSUK) and images from the Actors Archive of US. All these databases are free datasets that contain 2122 baseline faces and fingerprints.

4 Result

The quality, evaluation and missed data depend on the accuracy of the fusion decision which also depends on the quality of the comparison processes of the diverse modalities. The quality of the evaluation in each modality depends on different factors. These factors are affected by the quality of the captured biometric information (Figure

4), the quality of the stored biometric reference and the quality of the capturing device itself. The main capture is also dependent on the quality of the comparison algorithm and the structures used to characterize the biometrics. Another part which is also affected is the accuracy of the fusion algorithm, it is affected by the quality of the preprocessing of evaluation scores i.e. regularization. The biometric decision in verification is based only on one set of captured biometrics and one set (ID) of references. Nevertheless, under-identification, the decision depends on more than one set of biometric locations. This process leads to the belief that the identification scenario is more affected by the quality procedures, most especially in cases where the quality of biometrics references varies largely or is set to a significant value. Another reason to use multi-modal biometrics is the quest for advanced strength in biometric window systems.

This appears usually when considering the demand for biometric window systems, as well as designing pervasive biometric systems. The Multi-modal biometric window system is designed to be functional even when some information is missed, this directly affects the fusion algorithm proposal and has diverse effects under the confirmation and identification (ID) scenarios. Any misplaced biometric measure in a verification scenario can occur because of an unused captured biometric distinctiveness (Figure 5) or a missed reference within the externally claimed distinctiveness references set. During reference identification, a missed captured biometric measure, as well as a missed reference could occur due to misplaced information. Nevertheless, during identification where

Figure 4: A biometric window system with factors is affected by the quality of the captured biometric information.

the system steadily depends on a large number of reference sets, most missed modalities can be different in each comparison between each ID pair. The main condition maintains the development of more progressive and flexible resolutions for missing data under the ID scenario. Most presentation assessment of a multi-modal biometric system is not really different from that of predictable uni-modal biometric systems. The main identification results are usually shown or represented in a Cumulative Match Characteristic (CMC) curve, most especially when dealing with closed-set ID. The authentication routine is shown usually as an equal error rate (EER) and as a Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve.

Figure 5: An unused captured biometric distinctiveness.

5 Conclusion

This paper set out to investigate and capture a multi-modal biometric authentication system for people iden-

tification using a custom score fusion algorithm. There are a lot of defects in this type of authentication which is sometimes insecure than traditional forms of multi-factor authentication. This paper provides an inept means of design by automating the biometric mode as a form of multimodal authentication to counteract identity theft using a custom score fusion algorithm. It considers the facial features with the eye retina and fingerprint to accurately identify a person in multi-neutral settings involving a database of collected images. The future perspective is to demonstrate this in real-time and embed virtual image processing for online facial image recognition. The perspective is to use a deep learning search method to analyse people's demography and produce an error-free binary search for all input images.

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